

Decolonising the Map

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Maps present themselves as a clear, neutral way of making sense of the world, but each embodies a particular worldview which dictates how a territory is represented and what elements are included or excluded. Historically, this worldview has been that of a powerful controlling authority, such as that of colonial powers. This situation has not been improved by the mass-adoption of digital online maps: increasingly our experience of maps is becoming less diverse, with little chance of open participation in the production of spatial knowledge.

The development and application of digital technology is a part of cultural practice, and cannot be seen as just the linear progression of human knowledge. The choices made of how technologies should be used are linked to culturally-sited ideas of knowledge, understanding, and society, but these are rarely critically examined and are hidden by the seemingly acultural concept of 'progress'.

It is important that the politics of colonial oppression do not continue to operate quietly in form of a monolithic, dominant representation of the world. In the following, I will examine the history and development of maps, discuss the importance of different spatial stories, and introduce the Open Maps project which aims to 'decolonise the digital' by opening up (in a number of senses) the digital representation of built space.

The Emergence of the 'Objective' Map

Maps are the artefact of a process of 'making sense' of the world, and a way of communicating that process. We make maps to document a spatial understanding composed from the performance of not just geographical activities (exploration, traversal, measurement), but social, political, military, mercantile, cultural, et al. (negotiated borders, invaded territories, established trade routes, circulated travellers stories). Each map embodies its own particular viewpoint and tacit purpose.

Maps are transitory and fleeting, being contingent, relational and context-dependent; they are always mappings; spatial practices enacted to solve relational problems (e.g., how best to create a spatial representation, how to understand a spatial distribution, how to get between A and B, and so on).ⁱ

But maps no longer seem to be honest about their provisionality. Contemporary maps are the result of a gradual epistemological shift (a change in the way they present knowledge) that saw them transform from illustrations of a tour, an expedition, voyage of discovery, to a form that has removed any sign of the contingent activities that created it.

Early medieval maps were simple catalogues of itineraries – lists of performative indications primarily concerning pilgrimages – featuring stops that would be made, cities where the reader would pass through, spend the night in, pray at, etc., and with distances calculated in the hours or days it would take to cover them on foot.

Later maps visually represented geography with the addition of evocative illustrations: various symbols and paraphernalia – ships, animals, characters of all kinds – that weren't just decorative embellishments but gave insight into the stories of the maps' creation: "indicating the operations – travelling, military, architectural, political or commercial – that make possible the fabrication of a geographical plan [...] the sailing ship painted on the sea indicates the maritime expedition that made it possible to represent the coastlines."ⁱⁱ

As modern scientific discourse developed (from the fifteenth to the seventeenth century) the map slowly disengaged itself from the process of travel and exploration which was the condition of its creation. It became a tool of an Enlightenment mentality that attempted to sum something up as an object observed by an impartial, knowledgable, expert eye, articulating a desire to be a viewpoint and nothing more, comfortably distanced and disconnected from the the object of study and the chaotic messiness of the world. From this viewpoint, the map (having moved from itinerary or spatial story to an reification/objectification) 'made sense' of the world by surveying, ordering, labelling, pigeon-holing and categorising.

Enlightenment thought was strongly connected to the way Western colonial powers went about understanding external territories, but despite their development and extensive use of cartography in this process, the map itself isn't a creation of Western scientific rationality.

When the British arrived in South Asia, they found a well developed science of surveying and cartography, and the skilled set of experts who were essential for the British colonial project of mapping India. As in Europe, these maps formed the basis of taxation, administration, and control of land – "Powerful tools for aggressive governmental control of land as tax bases, natural resources, and national territories"ⁱⁱⁱ – in South Asia well before the arrival of the British. And as early as the 12C, examples of isometric representations of geography had been used by painters in China for surveying and making legible the territory of the Emperor.^{iv}

The dominant theme of the map is control. Those with the power to mobilise these skilled experts and their apparatus of surveying could reap the benefits for military, administrative, political, or economic purposes. For the British in Indian the map was a tool for all of these, needed to defend frontiers, navigate and operate trade routes, calculate potential tax revenue, and ensure the safety and regularity of communications.

Through Western colonialism the object of the map became external territories under control. While maps had existed in other cultures, the colonial use led to the emergence of the map as an 'objective' geographical representation. Maps formed part of a practice of colonial administration and Orientalist study: the transformation of vast heterogenous territories, people, cultures, and histories into a static object that could be analysed as a whole. Maps of the 'Orient' under British colonial rule codified, domesticated knowledge to be provided to the West.

The use of the map was transformed from a context-specific pragmatic description into a stand-in for study, where the map becomes the territory: a reifying, totalising object which "fed on and reinforced the colonial order".^v Along with the production of a legible model of geographical space, Enlightenment practices of colonial 'open air' sciences such as anthropology and phrenology made sense of people. The use of such 'rational' scientific study gave the colonial British the authority to claim they understood the history and nature of the Orient much more intimately than its indigenous people,^{vi} a claim used to justify a paternalistic, faux-philanthropic project of military dominance and oppression.

No longer just description, the map becomes an avatar, and exerts power through its reduction of reality. As part of an Orientalist studies, the reductive map influenced not only Western thought but that of the 'Orientals' too. But the map did more: by combining geographical knowledge with politically composed and constituted knowledge the map additionally became a form of proscription and declaration.

The act of drawing up boundaries on the map becomes the process of dividing up the physical territory of the world too. Through agreements such as the *Anglo-French Convention for delimitation of British and French possessions on Niger (1898)* the "inconvenient and unscientific boundaries" of the Lagos Colony, the Niger Coast Protectorate, and the Royal Niger Company were re-apportioned to become country borders drawn up without interest for geographical features, ethnic or language groups, or communities.^{vii} Two people from the same village – separated by a pond or a river – could find themselves in two different countries, with very different colonial administrations/laws.

From simple descriptions of spatial practices, the map had become an apparatus of power – operating in different 'modes of speech' at once: assertions of geographical features, declarations of borders and territory, and implicit or explicit directives for use of the territory based on the maps operational logic.

The City

The map privileges certain ways of conceptualising the world, and modes of ordering the world. It limits possible interpretations and ways of conceptualising space, drawing it out as an abstract representation, with elements cut from their bricks-and-mortar reality and reduced down to fit into a particular view of a functional city/territory/world, according to logic not explicitly declared but visible through absence and exclusion.

The power to view the world from a distance and as a whole has been compelling for cities as well as distant territories: artists had been representing a view of the city from far above well before it was a physical possibility. Thinking of the city as a single entity that must be understood and optimised has led to the adoption of a machinic model, with the concept of "The City"

as a whole providing "a way of conceiving and constructing space on the basis of a finite number of stable, isolatable, and interconnected properties".^{viii}

The problem here is the dissemination of an account of the city that begs the question (in the sense that it offers a strident answer along with the question) of the meaning of the city, which is dictated by the intentions and desires of powerful stakeholders (urban designers, architects, and law-makers) and insensitive to how people actually inhabit the space.

Those academics who feel strongly about it – such as philosophers Gilles Deleuze and Felix Guattari, Brian Massumi – say that it "limits the ways in which the target individual can connect with the individuals and objects with which it coexists. [...] They are] not only reactive but imperialist by nature." On the ground it disenfranchises and delegitimises people's ways of existing in the world, privileging the explicitly represented and going hand-in-hand with legal and physical restriction on the use of the city.

The architecture of city spaces tries to lock down certain uses. The landscape of Paris was radically transformed through Haussmannisation (with parallel urban projects in other European cities): levelling neighbourhoods of narrow streets and replacing them with the iconic, broad Parisian avenues that were intended to be impossible to barricade during armed uprisings by discontent residents.

These days cities have adopted anti-skate devices (e.g. metal studs and bars to prevent skateboarders 'grinding' on walls), anti-sleep devices (e.g. spikes placed on flat building surfaces, benches designed with armrests positioned to prevent their use as a bed), and even anti-youth devices (e.g. the Mosquito: a high-pitched noise-making device only audible to younger ears, used to drive off children and teenagers from particular public spaces).^{ix}

Between the prohibited, the 'anti-social', and remaining 'acceptable' ways of inhabiting the city some people are effectively excluded and dispossess, something articulated along class lines in David Harvey's re-visiting of Henri Lefebvre's concept of The Right to The City. But the basis for dictating how city space should be used is not just enacted along economic dividing-lines: the set of ways of inhabiting, spatial practices, interests and activities permitted in the city privilege specific cultural perspectives and reflect a history of colonial control.

Colonial powers enforced how colonial 'subjects' lived and the arrangement of towns. From 1513 the layout of Spanish Colonial towns was dictated via royal ordinance to specify how were built and organised, according to an idealised concept of virtuous civic life,^x and these were in turn followed for the Spanish settlements built to house forcefully-relocated indigenous populations. Likewise, the French program to 'resettle' dispossessed Algerians similarly built settlements on a uniform, disciplined grid, with a central square containing "the characteristic triad of French villages: school, town hall, and war memorial."^{xi} In a more contemporary example, the decision of contemporary Indigenous Australians to continue living in remote communities on country has been attacked as a "lifestyle choice" which is no longer financially sustainable or viable according to a recent Prime Minister Tony Abbott.^{xii}

From external territories to the city, maps have continued to be a mechanism of control, reinforcing dominant meanings of place.

The Digital Context

The spaces of modern cities are becoming progressively more legible and striated, facilitated by mapping, navigation, and documentation technologies such as Google Maps and location-aware devices. The emergence of these technologies has resulted in a city 'augmented' by digital technology and spatial practices that increasingly inhabit digital, virtual space.

The emergence of Google Maps as the de facto map provider has dampened the hopes of challenging a monolithic knowledge-authority, at least as far as cartography goes. Google's dominance has led to a homogenisation of cartographic choices as their competitors underwent a "Googlification", adopting the same mapping conventions, emulating their fonts, symbols, colour scheme, road width, etc.^{xiii}

The patents and monopolising tendencies of online service providers, mobile device manufacturers, et al. operate to restrict the possible forms of digital representation of space, and focus the remaining services into a rarified commercial 'market'. This neoliberal logic has produced a private corporation with the sheer power to mobilise cartographic science in a way that was once

only possible via state power, developing and utilising mapping technologies and expertise for rewards from commercial, civil sources, and state defence contracts.

Google Maps has achieved a remarkable colonial outcome: to turn the entirety of the world into a single, homogenous object for analysis. The imperialist overtones of this project resonate in the application of a particular Silicon-Valley-centric logic of space – one way of ‘making sense’ of the world – to every city, town, and village in the world, regardless of the particularities of local ways of inhabiting those spaces, or (via satellite imagery-based cartography) complicity, involvement, or even awareness of the process.

With the widespread adoption of internet-enabled smartphones, hand-drawn maps (e.g. crudely-sketched napkin directions, far removed from the aesthetic of the standardised map and overflowing with expression of context and improvisation) have all but died out.

Google Maps (through its near-universal use in embedded mobile applications and websites) provides a theoretical unified globe-space for representing all spatial information on earth, inspired in part by the fictional software product “Earth” from sci-fi novel *Snow Crash*:

[...]A globe about the size of a grapefruit, a perfectly detailed rendition of Planet Earth, hanging in space at arm's length in front of his eyes. [...] the user interface that [the privatised intelligence agency] uses to keep track of every bit of spatial information that it owns — all the maps, weather data, architectural plans, and satellite surveillance stuff.^{xiv}

Google Earth is the perfect image of what could be described as ‘ubiquitous space’: a seductive mythology of voyeurism and omniscience that has charmed many with the prospect of observing an object in extreme detail from an isolated, untouchable viewpoint. In practice as in sci-fi fantasy this is a totalising object of analysis and control.

Different stories

But people still manage to inhabit spaces in ways different to what is dictated: the map is not the territory!

There is still room in our cities for practices of inhabitation that go against the proscriptive desires of those in power (e.g. urban designers, etc.), beyond the “programmed and regulated operations”. When we ignore these ready-made meanings of spaces that maps provide, inhabiting space in spite of them, against a homogenous, *a priori* meaning of the city, we are practicing a very different type of ‘making sense’.

Alternative ways of using space can come out of radical (often playful) imaginings of the city, but mostly they are performed out of necessity. While there has been a long tradition of more holistic accounts of our experience of space (e.g. Gaston Bachelard’s exploration of the oneric image of home in *Poetics of Space*) and encouraging ‘critical spatial practices’ (e.g. the Situationist International’s experiments with mapping “psychogeography”^{xv}, or the generation of “Radical Cartographies”), everyday use of space actively resists homogenising and disciplining forces. The dominant representations of the use/meaning/ways of experiencing the city are specifically sited in a particular class, gender, ethnicity, and while some play, hide, dream, or get lost as a way of generating their own meaningful sense of it, others are just trying to ‘make do’.

Google Maps may happily provide you with the same set of directions through the world as anyone else, but in reality paths are opened and closed depending on who you are. The flaneur has been romanticised as an iconic Parisian mode of experiencing the city (a sensual, voyeuristic enjoyment of the sights and sounds of a busy metropolis), but the flaneur was sited in a position of privilege and security, and has been called out as being a mode of experience reserved exclusively for a particular gender (male), ethnicity (white), class (bourgeois), and social attributes (mobility and aloofness being primary).^{xvi} Likewise, by universalising the map and removing it from context, Google has create an fictional, impossible, normative figure, for whom the map provides navigation needs. The city may look very different for women at night, keeping to select well-lit streets and those who are not wealthy consumers who may be unwelcome in the tourist-centric areas of the city.

Radical spatial practices such as squatting and graffiti allow disenfranchised inhabitants of the city – those with no hope of owning property or having a say in the controlling official discourse of how the city should be used – to have find their own space. But others may have less oppositional alternative stories which are simply ways of ‘making sense’ and ‘making do’ within a framework of privileged uses they are is not part of.

The overwhelming effect of these spatial stories is to enrichen an account of geographical space, which challenges the dominance and normalising effect of a single monolithic representation of the city. Not presenting one way of understanding the world as a substitute for another, but as supplementary.

Open Maps: Decolonising the Digital

What sort of technologies are researched and developed, and the forms the resulting devices take are aspects of a cultural practice. The discussion of new technologies is normally framed around the creation of more refined and sophisticated tools, or optimised processes for recording, ordering or analysing, but the basis for their production is a specific worldview that generates ‘problems’ and ‘solutions’ according to specific ideas of politics, economics, nature, the civitas, etc. Through the history of maps, the problems being solved have been focussed around questions of effective control and extraction of revenue from territories.

Though it is usual to see emerging technologies put to the task of capture and analysis, this is simply a dominant culture of use, a self-nourishing ideology. Like the space of the city, the meaning and utility of these technologies are defined by how they are used, not given.

Through my fellowship with the Research Institute of Art and Technology (RIAT), I have been exploring methods of ‘decolonising the digital’: projects that counter colonial thinking and forms of representation in their uses of technology. This decolonising can be considered in two parts:

a) Counter claims: Articulating culturally-informed alternative uses of digital technology, that produce new aesthetics. Interested in the productive, creative use of technologies outside of a dominant Western cultural paradigm. Counter claims challenge a knowledge-authority’s self-declared right to dictate how something is represented, and what is necessary and sufficient in that representation.^{xvii} Radical cartographies are a form of counter-claim.

b) Reframing the mechanics of the technology itself: Attempting to explore the use of digital technology without mobilising it as a colonising technology, i.e. resisting the drive towards ‘capture’ and control (mapping, analysis, optimisation).

‘Gonzo’ research

Even in subversive re-appropriations of technology, there is a tendency for the results to operate with a similar totalising claim to authority as the original. For example, while Radical Cartography does not make this explicit claim, the aesthetic conventions of the modern map make it hard to acknowledge provisionality and plurality in their representations.

My own methodology of ‘Gonzo’ research attempts to move beyond the usual mechanics of knowledge-production that are at work with counter claims: the deconstruction of the others’ claim, and presentation of your own as truth. Inspired by the practice of ‘fictocritique’ in contemporary post-colonial anthropology, and ‘Gonzo’ journalism as a disavowal of the legitimacy of ‘objective’, ‘neutral’ account of the facts, Gonzo research tries to compose tentative, subjective, contingent stories.^{xviii}

The products of digital mapping technologies suffer from the same pathology as colonial maps: implicit claims to authority, expertise, and impartiality and an effacement or obfuscation of the contingency of their creation:

Every act of data collection is the act of hiding something. Because data fundamentally contains within it this question of somebody making the decision to measure here and not there, now and not then, with this instrument or that instrument but not this one. [...] We should ask] that question of who makes that decision, how do they make that decision, and why is it not ‘we’ making that decision [...] Who is it that decides what way to map any bit of data that excludes any other bit of data onto any kind of decision-making process at all [and] what is there motive?^{xix}

Gonzo research talks of outcomes that are “Performative” (revealing its subjectivity and contingency), “Creative/vitalist” (composing a new way of bringing things together or thinking about things rather than trying to categorise the world into ready-made systems), “Multiple” (or one-of-many: provisional, tentative), and “ecological” (not isolating out elements along lines of normal consideration or field).

Practicing gonzo research allows the creation of counter-claims, but also

resists the totalising nature of these technologies by acknowledging the radical subjectivity from which they were produced, e.g. by refusing the drive of digital mapping technologies to capture.

Open Maps

Open Maps is a project that was developed as part of the RIAT fellowship exploring ‘decolonising the digital’. The Open Map devices host digital online maps via WiFi and are build around \$5 Raspberrry Pi Zero computers, using open source software. The devices show up as an open WiFi network (many phones/devices will give a notification that it has found an open WiFi network), and users choosing to connect are automatically forwarded to the hosted map.

Mapping has traditionally been the tool of the powerful. The colonial mapping project took control of diverse, heterogenous mapping practices, and disciplined and coerced them into the production of a useful map. Control of Intellectual Property was a central issue even in the early days of colonial map-making, with the frustrated *East India Company* directors in London writing frequently to express consternation over instances of official survey maps making their way into the hands of private collectors. Until recently, the technologies used for hosting and accessing maps was carefully controlled through propriety software and Application Programming Interface (API) keys.

Through the use of free, open source software, and cheap, easily available hardware, the barrier to producing and disseminating digital maps is effectively removed. Open Maps exist as part of the emancipatory project of Open Hardware and Software initiatives which liberate the technical apparatus of spatial representation. In the context of ‘technology as cultural practices’ these projects allow a fracturing of the technological monoculture that had come from the institutional power needed to develop and wield these technologies and the pervasive ideology of Silicon Valley tech culture. They allow grassroots participation in the process of ‘making sense’ of and through digital technologies.

These maps do not need to have grand ambitions. Even the most humble, parochial scope succeeds as an example that the local and subjective perspective is valuable and legitimate. Such maps are the digital equivalent of the ‘hand-drawn directions on a napkin’ which embrace their own provisionality and expressivity. They tell spacial stories which are useless as a tool of productive consumer society (they don’t direct tourists to landmarks, don’t help the business man get to their meeting) but which help to understand the world in a richer way – a way informed by a sensitivity to emotions, memories, association, and mythology.

Open Maps exist in physical architecture, occupying public space outside of a dynamic of monopolised representation of the online services, more like graffiti than billboards and counter to Google Maps’ ‘ubiquitous spatiality’. To see them, one must share the intimate space generated by their WiFi signal. As tools of Gonzo research they present themselves as partial, localised accounts of the spaces they reside within and tell stories about. In this case – for a change – the map is contingent on the territory.

Notes

i Rob Kitchin and Martin Dodge, “Rethinking Maps,” *Progress in Human Geography* 31, no. 3 (2007): 331.

ii Spatial theorist Michel de Certeau gives a fantastic account of the history of maps, and the politics of power and knowledge that play out in the various ways of representing space in de Certeau, Michel. *The Practice of Everyday Life*. Translated by Steven Rendal. Los Angeles: University of California Press, 202.

iii Raj, Kapil. “Circulation and the emergence of modern mapping: Great Britain and early colonial India, 1764–1820.” In *Relocating Modern Science*, pp. 60-94. Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2007: 62 69.

iv For example see *Along the River During Qing Ming Festival* – 18C remake of 12C Song Dynasty original. In addition, there is at least one known example of a world atlas: “[comprising] thirty-four map sheets, made according to Persian cylindrical projection techniques, contained within a seventeenth-century (1647) encyclopaedic work, Shadid-i Sadiq, by Muhammad Sadiq ibn Muhammad Salih of Jaunpur (also known as Sadiq Isfahani)”, though this was probably intended more as decorative curiosity rather than a reference tool (Kapil, p85).

v Raj, p63.

vi Former British Prime Minister Arthur James Balfour appealed to the British parliament saying “We know the civilisation of Egypt better than we know the civilisation of any other country. We know it further back; we know it more intimately; we know more about it.” This sentiment of being capable of more insight due to rational investigation and external perspective is a claim to authority still visible in non-critical anthropological studies. (see Said, Edward. “Orientalism.” (1978), Penguin, 2003: 32.)

vii Carland, John M., *The Colonial Office and Nigeria, 1898-1914*: 50.

viii de Certeau, 94.

ix Charlotte Walsh, “The Mosquito: A Repellent Response,” *Youth Justice* 8, no. 2 (2008): 122.

x Mumford, Jeremy Ravi (2014). *Vertical Empire: The Grand Resettlement of Indians in the Colonial Andes*. Duke University Press. 67.

xi Bourdieu, Pierre, and Franz Schultheis. *Picturing Algeria*. Columbia University Press, 2012: 73.

xii Medhora, Shalailah, “Remote communities are ‘lifestyle choices’, says Tony Abbott.” *The Guardian*, Tuesday 10 March 2015.

xiii Timothy R Wallace, “Google Maps: Homogenizing Our Landscape” (paper presented at the *Is Google Good for Geography?* Web 2.0 and the Political Economy of User Generated Geographical Knowledge, Las Vegas, USA, 2009).

xiv Neil Stephenson, *Snow Crash* (New York: Bantam Books,1993), 106.

xv Though the gender element is contended, the status as ‘consumers’ is fundamental. D’souza, Aruna, and Tom McDonough. *The invisible Flâneuse?: Gender, public space, and visual culture in nineteenth-century Paris*. Manchester University Press, 2006.

xvi De Certeau describes the influence of the unconscious on our experience of the city: “The childhood experience that determines spatial practices later develops its effects, proliferates, floods private and public spaces, undoes their readable surfaces, and creates within the planned city a “metaphorical” or mobile city, like the one Kandinsky dreamed of: “a great city built according to all the rules of architecture and then suddenly shaken by a force that defies all calculation.’ (de Certeau, 110)

xvii I have written elsewhere about the specific case of Indigenous rock art, where it is deeply problematic for archaeologists to claim authority through their position as institutional experts, and use that to justify unilateral control of how rock art is represented and what is considered worthy of documentation.

xviii Harle, Josh, *Making Sense: Tactics, Hacking, and Gonzo Research*, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.31961, Tactical Space Lab, Sydney, 2015

xix Hague, Usman, *Big Bang Data – Who controls our data?*, Somersethouse, 2015.

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Josh Harle is a multidisciplinary researcher and new media artist with a background in Computer Science, Philosophy, and Sculpture. His research investigates the virtual spaces generated by emerging technologies, our encounters with the world through them, and their social and political consequences.

Harle’s practice explores the contemporary use of digital technologies to map and make sense of the world, critiquing the opaquely ideological practice of digital capture. His works take various established and emerging mapping technologies – laser scanning, photogrammetry, geolocation tracking – and re-appropriates them as expressive mediums, altering their outcomes to introduce an affective element which is normally absent. The results embrace their performative origins and the contingency of their creation.

Through these radical cartographic practices, Harle reveals his own place in a field of competing drives to organise, stake-claims, and dictate boundaries: the map as a performance of exploration, of trying to make sense of the world.